
GENDER DIFFERENCES IN ADVERSITY QUOTIENT AMONG INMATES IN DELTA STATE, NIGERIA

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A B S T R A C T	KEY WORDS
<p>This study is to determine the influence of gender on the Adversity Quotient of inmates in Delta State. One research question and corresponding hypothesis guided the study. The design of the study was a descriptive research design. A sample of 525 inmates was drawn from a population of 7,348 inmates in all the custodian centres in Delta State. The researchers adopted purposive and non-proportionate stratified simple random sampling techniques for the sample size determination. The instrument for the study was titled Adversity Quotient Scale for Prisoners (AQSP). The AQSP is made up of 96 items delineating inmates feeling adversity. Almost half of the items of the AQSP were positively keyed while the other half was negatively keyed. The face and content validities of the instrument were established. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained using internal consistency reliability via Cronbach Alpha technique. A coefficient of 0.95 was obtained. Data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation, independent sample t-test technique. The results showed that there was a significant difference between the male and female inmates on their Adversity Quotient. This implies that there is nothing to worry about when comparing the adversity level of male and female inmates. The study therefore recommended among others that prison warders should encourage the inmates by giving assignments on biographies of people within and outside the immediate environment of inmates who have distinguished themselves through dint of discipline, hard-work and sheer bravery.</p>	<p>adversity quotient, gender, inmates, correctional centres.</p>

INTRODUCTION

Human existence, from time immemorial has been permeated by adversities necessitated by some life paradoxes and push factors leading to stress and anxiety that tend to demand tougher psychological skills and attention for virtually everyone to survive in a society (Bakare, 2015).

Adversity is about a state of hardship and affliction, misfortune, calamitous event, conflict, distress or an unfortunate event or incident. It could be both a general condition and a specific situation (Bakare, 2015). Adversity in most cases could be attributed to be part of human endeavours, and can be faced by people at any given time, irrespective of demographic diversities.

This goes to explain why people get into unwanted situation (possibly troublesome one) as they are unable to contain and manage the level of adversity they face – which consequently leads to taking actions and committing offences against persons and state – resulting to incarceration and recidivism, due to some push factors (Ugwuoke, 1993; Ahire, 2004). Arguing in this direction, Stoltz (1997, 2010) submits that people of each age class face diverse adversities exclusive to them with respect to instance and space; and most time, when it is poorly handled, it earns them different punishments. This greatly explains why people are imprisoned most times. In a society where push factors abound, adversity never ceases. It is taken as part of people's life, and has become the significant reason why people are incarcerated in Nigeria and world over (Ugwuoke, 1993; AlSiebert, 2005).

Challenges, misfortunes, difficulties or adversity makes a person tougher. Unfortunately, when faced with life's challenges, most people stop before trying to do their best and know the limits of ability. Adversity can be a bridge to success if individuals are able to convert every difficulty into a challenge. The ability to deal with adverse situation is termed Adversity. It is the ability one has in facing ones difficulties and obstacles in order to overcome and survive in the society. Adversity can be interpreted as difficulty, misfortune, suffering related to difficulty, or o trauma (Jackson, Firtko & Edenborough, 2007; Harriman, 2016).

Stoltz & Weiheimayer (2010) defined adversity as a negative impact, on someone or something you care about. Luthar & Cicchetti, as cited in Harriman (2016), defines adversity as encompassing negative life circumstances with difficulty in adjustment. Difficulty is the consequence of an individual's failure to adjust to the demands of change (Tugade & Fredrickson, 2004; and Harriman, 2016). From some of the above meanings, adversity has elements: difficult conditions, suffering, negative experiences, or events both traumatized and traumatic facing individuals. Perceptions about the difficult conditions vary from person to person. One kind of difficulty can be considered small for a person, but considered a big and serious for others (Harriman, 2016; and Cuff, 2017).

The individual judging an event is considered to be disadvantageous depending on:

- (1) How big is the impact of the adversity;
- (2) Potential severity resulting from difficulty; and
- (3) How important it is to a person (Stoltz & Weiheimayer, 2010:37; Cuff, 2017).

Given that the consequence of adversity is adverse, people's struggle against it continues from childhood into adult life (Stoltz, 2000). He goes further to affirm in one of his studies that the number of adversities an individual faces each day on an average has increased from seven (7) to twenty-three (23) in the last 10 years. Difficulties, or in this term called adversity, should make a person tougher. Unfortunately, when faced with life's challenges, most people stop before trying to do their best and know the limits of ability. Adversity can be a bridge to success if individuals are able to convert every difficulty into a challenge.

The ability to deal with adversity is termed Adversity Intelligence or Adversity Quotient. Individuals with high levels of adversity quotient are categorized as Climbers. Individuals with moderate adversity intelligence, categorized as Campers. The third group is Quitters, i.e. groups that are left behind in the Climbers. AQ can play a role in providing a description related to how a person's ability to survive in facing difficulties and being able to overcome them. According to Stoltz In Diana, Ade, Etihi and Ilmi (2019), in AQ level, there are three types of people facing difficulties and obstacles, namely the type of Quitters who give up when overcoming obstacles, the type of Campers who are satisfied with the results and the type of Climbers who have courage in every effort

whatever obstacles they face in achieving success. Gender differences have significantly different abilities in responding to difficulties.

According to Black's Law Dictionary, an inmate is an individual who is dispossessed of his freedom against his will, kept in internment or detention in a jail for the conviction of a crime. An inmate's response to adversity may be determined by personal characteristics and environmental factors. The meaning of gender can be categorized as sex and gender. Sex is "male or female physical sex characteristic decided by chromosomes"; gender "means individuals' psychological identification of male or female". It is their individual subjective perceptions of masculinization and feminization, and a kind of gender identification (Basow, 1992). For Thornton and Freedman in Chao (2014), gender is an ascribed status or status that can be at birth. According to WHO (World Health Organization), gender is a category of men.

An inmate's response to adversity may be determined by personal characteristics and environmental factors. Stoltz (2010) argues that one's response to adversity is formed through the influence of parents, peers, and other key people. Furthermore, people's response to adversity can be interrupted and permanently changed, due to some factors; sometimes their responses to adversity are learned (Dweck, 2012) and women (McGinn & Oh, 2017; WEF, 2017). Gender refers to socially constructed roles, behaviors, activities, and attitudes deemed by a particular society appropriate for men and women (Chalabaev, *et. al.*, 2013; Chin & Hung, 2013). Fisher (2011) also stated that men and women have many of the same characteristics; differences are seen only from personality types, most men have a steering personality type (associated with testosterone hormone activity), they tend to have self-control, researching options carefully without emotion, happy to compete, more systematic, analytical, logical and straightforward, and tend to be easier to choose than women (Fisher, 2001; Albert, Carre & Arnocky, 2016; Andelin & Rusu, 2016).

Women are mostly negotiated (associated with estrogen hormone activity), which has a way of thinking (web thinking), the ability to think by analyzing various factors, have a high sense sensitivity, intuitive, encouragement to give the right response to the needs of others, the ability to realize everything that happens around, always encouraged to give, and always helping others (Fisher, 2011, Meyers-Levy & Loken, 2015). M.E.P. Seligman (1972), as cited in Harriman (2016), states women are twice as likely to be depressed than men. Women also tend to analyze to ponder to what is wrong; whereas the other man, distracts them, and refuses to think of a temporary problem (Seligman, 1972; and Harriman, 2016). Dweck (2005), as cited in Enriquez & Estacio (2009), also shows that girls respond to many different things from boys to the criticism they receive from teachers and colleagues (Dweck, 2005; Enriquez & Estacio, 2009).

Girls learn to associate their failures with permanent traits, (because they are stupid, unable to), whereas boys learn to link their failures with more temporary resources, such as lack of motivation and less attention (Wright, Mannathoko & Pasic, 2006; Harriman, 2016). Based on these facts, this study aims to examine the influence of gender on the adversity quotient of inmates. Studies have shown that Gender will affect Adversity Quotient. When faced with difficulties, female tend to blame themselves and male usually focus on the results of these difficulties. Male and female students have different characteristics because of physiological and psychological factors. Stoltz (2002) suggested that different genders have significantly different capacities in response to adversity. When encountering adversity, females tend to blame themselves and males usually focus on the result of adversity. Based on research there are differences between male and female in dealing with adversity This is due to various factors that make gender differences in this study aims to determine the influence of gender on Adversity Quotient of inmates.

Diana, Ade, Etih, and Ilmi (2019) conducted research on the relationship between high school students' learning outcomes and their adversity quotient and gender. The sample size was 114 pupils from SMA Negeri College who were used in this study, which was done there. Ex post facto 3x2 factorial design was the technique utilized. The adversity quotient and learning outcome instrument was used to collect the data. Data had a homogeneous variance and a normal distribution. The findings revealed that there was a substantial difference in the average student learning outcome for the three types of students studied: quitters, campers, and climbers. Climbers learned more than campers or those who gave up; that the average student's learning outcome differed significantly between male and female pupils and female pupils performed better academically than male students; and the Adversity Quotient and Gender variables did not interact.

Visayas, Philippines, Calles and Loreta (2015) explored the association between academic administrators' personal qualities and their AQ. Respondents comprised of 108 administrators from chosen state universities and colleges in Eastern Visayas Region. A questionnaire that elicited personal attributes and AQ was used to collect the data. The CORE (control, ownership, reach, and endurance) dimensions were used to gauge the level of AQ. The majority of academic administrators were married women in their middle years of life. The respondents have doctoral degrees as their greatest level of education, and they have been working in academia for more than 21 years in positions ranging from Associate Professor. Results showed that respondents generally had low AQ, which indicates that they have a limited ability to overcome difficulties and problems. The best indicators of reach are age, social standing, and greatest level of education. Only academic standing was a reliable indicator of perseverance. The respondents' reach and degree of control were significantly correlated with their adversity quotient.

Sigit, Suryanda, Suprayanti, and Zjulilh (2019) conducted research on how gender and the degree of hardship affected high school students' learning outcomes in terms of biodiversity. 114 pupils chosen at random from SMA Negeri 1 Cibinong were included in the study. Ex-post facto of 3 x 2 factorial designs were the technique employed and adversity quotient and learning outcome instrument was used to collect the data. Data had a homogeneous variance and a normal distribution. The findings indicated that the average student learning outcome for the types of quitters, campers, and climbers varied significantly. Climbers learned more than campers or those who gave up. The average student learning outcome between male and female pupils differed significantly. Female pupils performed better academically than male students. Finally, there was no connection between gender and adversity quotient and how well students learned about biodiversity.

In order to develop a measuring device for research on college students, Bingquan, Weisheng, Xudong, and Wenxiu (2019) conducted a study on the development of the adversity quotient scale for college students. 578 students were used in the study as the sample size; they were chosen at random from 4 regional universities in the Guangdong Province. They used project analysis, exploratory factor analysis, and confirmatory factor analysis as their methods of analysis. Confirmatory factor analysis revealed that the six factor models that were selected from the data fit the data well ($\chi^2/df = 2.595$, NNFI = 0.835, RMSEA = 0.058, CFI = 0.844, RMR = 0.07, GFI =

0.814, AGFI = 0.794) - Each scale dimension's dependability coefficient ranges from 0.684 to 0.917.

The association between the social adaptation scale (SAS) and the adversity quotient scale was 0.291 which was significant at the level of 0.01. As a result of the study's findings, it is recommended to use the adversity quotient scale as a useful tool to assess students' inverse quotients in colleges because it has high reliability and validity. In relation to the current study, it is important to note that Bingquan, Weisheng, Xudong, and Wenxiu's (2019)

study shares some dimensions with ours, even though it did not take into account the creation, validation, and use of an adversity quotient test for inmates in Nigerian correctional facilities.

Yakoha, Chongrukasaa, and Prinyapola (2015) analyzed data from 116 kids aged 8 to 21 in order to analyze the relationship between parenting styles and the adversity quotient of youth at the Pattani foster home in Thailand. According to the analysis, all of the sampled students had moderate exposure to all four parenting philosophies, with authoritarian practice receiving the highest average marks. Additionally, it was discovered that the students' adversity quotients were low and that there was a weak correlation between parenting practices and adversity quotients that ranged from mild to moderate. As a result, the study unequivocally advised authoritative parenting as a reagent for raising the adversity quotient for children in Pattani.

From the result, it could be discerned that because such an approach encourages adolescents and adults to maintain boundaries and controls over their actions and inactions, it is contended that the use of authoritative parenting styles appears to be similar to the nature and practice of prison services prior to their conversion to correctional facilities. This is based on the idea that people with authoritative parents are more likely to be outgoing, competent, responsible, and autonomous when dealing with their wards, children, and care recipients. They are also less likely to externalize behaviors and are less likely to use drugs than people with uninvolved parents (Gonzalez, Holbein, & Quilter, 2002; Steinberg & Silk, 2002).

Thi (2007) analyzes the big five to determine the adversity quotient in an effort to predict work performance. The study investigates a notion known as the Adversity Quotient using both theoretical and empirical methods (AQ). It contends that the five component model, also known as the "big five," can be used to understand various aspects of human potential and performance. Data were obtained from Det Norske Veritas and CORE Learning in order to carry out the study's task, and a total of 98 individuals were chosen from a heterogeneous sample population that included 57 men and 41 women. Based on the analysis, the study's findings indicate that the overall score of AQ's assessment instrument (ARP) does not accurately predict job performance above the level of the big five. Nevertheless, the study contends that theory significantly supports the AQ framework. In conclusion, it makes the case that AQ measurement, practical application, and AQ theory should all be used in tandem to evaluate job performance.

Self-esteem and optimism are investigated by Marc, Reyes, Dillague, Fuentes, Malicsi, Manalo, and Ryan (2020) within a sample of Filipino active duty military soldiers stationed in military camps as potential indicators of resilience. The study's inspiration came from the extreme physical and psychological stress that military troops experience as well as the fact that the psychology literature on stress, adversity, and its effects is dominated by the effects of resilience, optimism, and self-esteem. The study highlights the predictive value of self-esteem and optimism for resilience. Fergus and Zimmerman's Resilience Theory (2005) holds that people have innate attributes like resilience that enables them to survive hardship.

By using a predictive non-experimental research design, the study provides deeper insight into mental health issues that were previously thought to be too superficial and frequently rejected. The study attempts to determine whether self-esteem and optimism can predict resilience using 360 military troops on activity duty. It used a non-probability technique by completing a test battery made up of the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, the Life Orientation Test-Revised (LOT-R), and the Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale to gauge the variables (CD-RISC). The study reveals that significant findings indicated a relationship between the research variables and that resilience among the present study's selected active duty military members in military camps is predicted by self-esteem and optimism.

Diana, Ade, and Ilmi (2019) evaluated how gender and the adversity quotient (AQ) affected the learning outcomes of an article written by high school students. With the aim of determining how the adversity quotient and gender affect high school students' learning outcomes regarding biodiversity, three types of AQ - quitters, campers, and climbers - were used. A sample of 114 students was selected through simple random sampling, and an *ex post facto* 3 x 2 factorial design was used. The adversity quotient and learning outcome instrument was used to collect the data. Data had a homogeneous variance and a normal distribution. The revealed results showed that the average student learning outcome on types of quitters, campers, and climbers varied significantly. Climbers learned more than campers or those who gave up. The average student learning outcome between male and female pupils differed significantly. Female pupils performed better academically than male students. Adversity Quotient and gender had no effect on how well students learned about biodiversity from the course material. IQ, emotional intelligence, and spiritual intelligence were examined by Animasahun (2010) as indicators of jail adjustment among convicts in Nigerian prisons. Four hundred and fifty eight male and forty-two female inmates, randomly chosen from five prisons in Nigeria, were used for the study. *Ex-post facto* correlation research design was used in the study. The three research topics posed in the study were tested using data analyzed using multiple regression analysis and Pearson product moment correlation.

With emotional intelligence leading the way ($r = 0.95$), spiritual intelligence coming in second ($r = 0.83$), and intelligent quotient coming in third ($r = 0.79$), the results revealed strong positive correlations between the independent variables and jail adjustment. Additionally, the three independent factors made up 93.2% of the criterion (Prison Adjustment), while the relative contributions were Emotional Intelligence ($B = 0.736$), Spiritual Intelligence ($B = 0.443$), and Intelligent Quotients ($B = 0.173$), as shown by the Beta results. In light of this, Jimoh (2007) stated that everyone contains each type of intelligence in varying degrees, allowing people to live either productively or unproductively in their surroundings.

In order to determine the connection between prisoners' self-esteem, needs-satisfaction, and psychological well-being, Bruce and Larweh (2017) looked at inmates' self-esteem, needssatisfaction, and psychological well-being in James Camp Prison in Ghana. The study used the correlation survey design method to gather data from respondents who are inmates at the Accra, Ghana-based James Camp Prison. 155 male prisoners were chosen by the random selection method out of a total population of 347. The results showed that among prisoners, self-esteem, needs fulfillment, and psychological well-being are significantly positively correlated. The number of years a prisoner spends behind bars has no bearing on how mentally healthy they are, and visiting from family and friends has had little impact either. In order to lessen the psychological impacts of imprisonment on inmates, it is advised that counseling be reinforced in prisons.

The Sustainable Development Goals emphasize attaining sustainable development, and Eva-Maria, Werner, and Christoph (2019) conducted a study that designed and validated an instrument for measuring student sustainability abilities (SDGs). One thousand six hundred twenty-two kids who participated in the survey and ranged in age from 9 to 16 were used in the study. According to the study's findings, secondary schools can test sustainability competencies using the evaluation tool that has been provided. Through the operationalization of sustainability skills, the demands and successes of ESD implementation in schools are made clear by the obtained insights.

In order to ascertain the state of rehabilitation services in Nigerian prisons in Edo State, Asokhia and Osumah (2013) conducted an assessment of those services. Two research questions were posed in order to address the issue that sparked the study. The study included 147 prisoners from the six Nigerian prisons in the Edo State as part of a survey research design. A checklist known as "Rehabilitation Services in Nigerian Prisons in Edo State

(RSNPES)" was given to the participants as a means of gathering data (prison inmates). Simple percentage was chosen as the research methodology, and analysis of the results showed that provision of rehabilitation services is still ignored and does not adhere to worldwide best practices, and prisoners in these jails favor one form of rehabilitation over another.

The survey clearly shows that football is the most popular recreational activity for recovery. In light of the findings, it was suggested, among other things, that the Federal Government and prison service providers make concerted efforts to improve Nigeria's jail system and bring it into compliance with worldwide best practices. In order to rehabilitate prisoners and prevent recidivism, it is also necessary to establish more rehabilitation services, facilities, and reformative programs, such as teaching inmates how to use information and communication technology (ICT), providing proper awareness campaigns as prison inmates were observed to prefer one rehabilitation program or activity over another (Enuku, 2001).

Sanjuan-Meza, Landeros-Olvera and Cossio-Torres (2018), validated a resilience scale (RESI-M) in indigenous women in Mexico. The study argued that resilience encompasses a series of capacities and skills that individuals acquire through interaction with their context, thus succeeding in overcoming their own limits of resistance by generating more efficient defensive and protective mechanisms and processes than before when exposed to adverse events. Resilience is assessed by measuring the adverse situation, successful adaptation, and the process, which has led to the development of a variety of instruments. There is no instrument in the literature that contemplates resilience from the cultural perspective of indigenous women, so the aim of this study was to assess the validity and reliability of scores obtained with the scale in this population group.

An assessment of resilience (RESI-M) in indigenous women in Mexico was verified by SanjuanMeza, Landeros-Olvera, and Cossio-Torres (2018). The study argued that resilience encompasses a series of capacities and skills that individuals acquire through interaction with their context, thus succeeding in overcoming their own limits of resistance by generating more efficient defensive and protective mechanisms and processes than before when exposed to adverse events. Resilience is measured by taking into account the challenging circumstances, effective coping mechanisms, and process, which has resulted in the creation of numerous instruments. The goal of this study was to evaluate the validity and reliability of results from the scale in this demographic group because there is no instrument in the literature that considers resilience from the cultural perspective of indigenous women. On hundred and eighty (180) individuals from different indigenous communities in Mexico made up the sample and completed the Mexican Resilience Scale (RESI-M), which was created by Palomar Lever and Gómez Valdez in 2010. The Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient was used to evaluate internal consistency, and principal components factor analysis with Varimax rotation was used to identify the internal organization of each dimension. Participants' average age was 33 + 94 years. An acceptable reliability of 0.942 (Cronbach's alpha) and six factors that account for 56.34% of the total variance were obtained in the final version of the instrument, which consisted of 34 questions (down from the original 43 questions), following analysis of the reliability and statistical validity. With a structure that enables evaluating resilience as a process among indigenous women, the version is valid and dependable. The aim of this study is to investigate the influence of gender on the Adversity Quotient of Inmates in Delta State, Nigeria.

This research question guided the study

1. To what extent does gender influence Adversity Quotient of Inmates in Delta State?
This hypothesis tested at 0.05 alpha level also guided the study.

This hypothesis

1. Gender does not significantly influence Adversity Quotient of Inmates in Delta State.

METHODOLOGY

The research design of the study was a Descriptive Research Design. This type of research design is purely on a theoretical basis where the individual collects data, analyses, prepares and then presents it in an understandable manner. A sample of 525 inmates was drawn from a population of 7,348 inmates in all the custodian centres in Delta State. The researchers adopted purposive and non-proportionate stratified random sampling techniques for the sample size determination. A simple random sample is a subset of individuals chosen from a larger set in which a subset of individuals are chosen randomly, all with the same probability. Ninety-six (96) items were generated for the scale known as Adversity Quotient Scale for Prisoners (AQSP). The AQSP is made up of 96 items delineating inmates feeling adversity. Almost half of the items of the AQSP were positively keyed while the other half was negatively keyed.

The instrument is in the form of Likert scale format with 4 points response pattern: strongly agreed, agreed, strongly disagreed, disagreed weighted 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively for positive items and 4, 3, 2, 1 respectively for negative items. The face and content validities of the instrument were established. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained using internal consistency reliability via Cronbach Alpha technique. A coefficient of 0.95 was obtained. The instrument was administered to the sample in the locale under investigation. Data obtained were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research question while independent t–test analysis was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 significant level.

RESULTS

Research question: To what extent does gender influence Adversity Quotient of Inmates in Delta State?

Hypothesis: Gender does not significantly influence Adversity Quotient of Inmates in Delta State.

Table 1: Mean, standard deviation and independent t-test analysis of the influence of gender on AQS among inmates

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male	389	195.2	70.2	523	2.550	1.96	Significant
Female	136	206.6	83.4				

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of male and female inmates on Adversity Quotient as 195.2, 70.2; and 206.6, 83.4 respectively. Considering the mean scores for the males and females, it is evident that males and females differ in their mean rating of Adversity Quotient among inmates in Delta State. The result in the table also reveals that the t-calculated is greater than the t-critical of 1.96 at 523 degree of freedom and 0.05 alpha level. In light of this, the null hypothesis was rejected. The conclusion which is drawn from the result is that male and female inmates differ significantly in their Adversity Quotient.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The results revealed that there is a significant influence of gender difference on the adversity quotients of inmates. The results of this study are in line with research that suggests that those whose adversity quotient are high can face difficulties or obstacles and will not blame others regardless of the results of their efforts. This study showed the average value of male inmate is lower than female inmates. This is alleged because there are differences in the coping strategy of male and female inmates influenced by experience. This result is however supported by

(Fisher, 2011; Albert, Carre & Arnocky, 2016; Andelin & Rusu, 2016) who argue that women are mostly negotiated (associated with estrogen hormone activity), which has a way of thinking (web thinking), the ability to think by analyzing various factors, have a high sense sensitivity, intuitive, encouragement to give the right response to the needs of others, the ability to realize everything that happens around, always encouraged to give, and always helping others.

The result further reveals that significantly, gender influences adversity quotient of inmates in the state as the t-cal of 2.550 is greater than the t-critical of 1.96 at 0.05 significant levels. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis of no significant influence of gender on adversity quotient of inmates in Delta State, Nigeria. The rejection of the null hypothesis leads to the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis which states that there is significant influence of gender on adversity quotient of inmates in Delta State, Nigeria. By inference, the result suggests that the manner in which female and male inmates behave diverges to a reasonable extent; as such they are not seen as being the same. This is because their personal experience is not framed within a given socialization process and dynamic traits.

The result of our study is in line with report of Diana, *et. al.*, (2019), who conducted a study on the effects of adversity quotient and gender on learning outcomes of high school students on biodiversity. The study further reports that there is a significant difference between the averages of student's learning outcome on type quitters, campers, and climbers; the average student's learning outcome between male and female students; learning outcome of female students was higher than male students and there was no interaction between adversity quotient and gender. The result also commensurate with the study of Philippines, *et. al.*, (2015) on the relationship between academic administrators' personal characteristics and their AQ. Results revealed that in general, respondents have low AQ which indicate their low capacity to be resilient on adversities and challenges.

In order to buttress the results of our study, Diana, Ade, Etih, and Ilmi (2019) conducted research on the relationship between high school students' learning outcomes and their adversity quotient and gender and reported as that: there was a substantial difference in the average student learning outcome for quitters, campers, and climbers; average student's learning outcome differed significantly between male and female pupils; female pupils performed better academically than male students; and adversity quotient and gender variables did not interact. By interrogating the influence of gender on adversity quotient of students Sigit, Suryanda, Suprayanti, and Zjulilch (2019) observe that the average student learning outcome between male and female pupils differ significantly; and female pupils performed better academically than male students. However, there was no connection between gender and adversity quotient and how well students learned about biodiversity

Contrary to this result, (Harriman, 2016; Suprianto & Novanto, 2016; Verma, Aggarwal & Bansal, 2017) maintain that adversity quotient is not influenced by gender. Previous researchers have suggested contrary results that adversity intelligence between men and women does not differ significantly (Canivel, 2010; Cura & Gozum, 2011; Patdo, Mariano & Gonzales, 2011; Olila, 2012; Napire, 2013; Nikam & Megha, 2013; Ablana & Isidro, 2015; Bakare, 2015; Maureen, 2015).

CONCLUSION

The ability to respond positively to difficulties is a quality that every male or female inmate has to possess, because with this ability one will not easily give up and make the illusion as a way of success. This study also found out that those with higher degrees of gender roles have a higher Adversity Quotient.

Recommendations

Based on the findings the following recommendations were made;

1. The prison warders should encourage the inmates by giving assignments on biographies of people within and outside the immediate environment of inmates who have distinguished themselves through dint of discipline, hard work and sheer brevity.
2. They should be encouraged to learn from their examples and strive hard in overcoming difficulty situations and strengthening their survival instincts.
3. Male inmates should be advised to learn how to overcome difficult situations.

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